

Refractory behaviour in hydrogen atmospheres: insights for decarbonized direct reduction processes

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ABSTRACT

In response to the environmental challenges facing the 21st century, the direct reduction of iron (DRI) technology is projected to gain space in steel production, initially with the use of natural gas as reducing agent but with progressively higher amounts of H₂ added to the reducing gas, possibly up to 100%. As there is only limited precedent of industrial applications where refractories are exposed to atmospheres with such high levels of hydrogen content, the implications of these process changes for the durability of the refractory lining are still not fully comprehended. This work takes an experimental bottom-up approach to tackle this question, using high-temperature, multi-day hydrogen exposure tests under laboratory conditions to investigate the kinetics of reduction of ceramic oxides by hydrogen and provide mechanistic insights into corrosion. By identifying the key factors driving material degradation, this research will contribute to ensuring the reliability of refractories in hydrogen-based DRI for sustainable steel production.

INTRODUCTION

The switch from the coke-based blast furnace reduction of iron ore to hydrogen-based DRI could enable a substantial decrease in the CO₂ emissions associated with steelmaking [1]. In this context, it is important to ensure that the DRI vessels are lined with refractories capable of withstanding the new, strongly reducing conditions. It is known that refractory oxides can be reduced and volatilize under H₂ atmospheres, with silica being especially susceptible to corrosion [2].

The kinetics of the reduction of silica by hydrogen has been investigated by different authors [3 - 5]. The reaction only proceeds at a slow rate at the conditions encountered in DRI, but continued exposure over years of operation could entail significant damage. It is also possible that the corrosion kinetics will be accelerated by different factors, such as structural defects, surface hydroxylation, and the presence of impurities. In this study, we seek to determine the role of latter. Specifically, we investigate whether iron can catalyze the H₂ reduction of silica by exposing mixtures of quartz and hematite powders to a hydrogen atmosphere over extended periods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the experiments, high-purity quartz (99.995%; Sigma-Aldrich) and hematite (99.995%; Sigma-Aldrich) powders were used. The powders were weighed to a total of 1,000 mg per sample using an analytical balance and placed in fine alumina crucibles. The crucibles were placed in a sample holder, as shown in Figure 1. The first and last samples served as references, consisting of 100% SiO₂ and 100% Fe₂O₃, respectively. The intermediate samples contained mixtures of 95% SiO₂ with 5% Fe₂O₃, and 90% SiO₂ with 10% Fe₂O₃.

The samples were then inserted in a hydrogen tube furnace and heated under Ar at a rate of 200 °C/h. In sequence, they were exposed to a 100% H₂ flow at 100 L/h and held at 1200 °C for different lengths of time, from 25 to 100 h. Cooling was performed under argon to prevent reoxidation of the reduced

samples. Finally, the samples were weighed using an analytical balance.

A scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis of the powders with backscattered electrons was also performed before and after exposure to hydrogen.

Fig. 1: Samples: 100% SiO₂, 95% SiO₂ with 5% Fe₂O₃, 90% SiO₂ with 10% Fe₂O₃, and 100% Fe₂O₃, in fine alumina crucibles.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Full reduction of Fe₂O₃ to metallic Fe was achieved in all trials. This is demonstrated by the weight loss of the hematite. Considering the reduction reaction

it can be calculated that Fe₂O₃ will lose 30.1% of its weight upon full reduction to Fe. This value was consistently observed in the trials. Visually, the material went from a reddish-brown color to grey, and the powder underwent sintering (Fig. 2). The SEM analysis showed a uniform, fully reduced metallic material (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2: 100% Fe₂O₃ sample a) before exposure to hydrogen, b) after exposure to hydrogen, with full reduction to Fe.

Fig. 3: SEM of 100% Fe₂O₃ sample after exposure to hydrogen for 24 h at 1200 °C.

The pure silica powder, on the other hand, showed no observable changes. The SEM analysis likewise did not show any alterations in the material. It is known that silica can be reduced by hydrogen at 1200 °C, and the main product of reduction at this temperature is SiO:

The reduction of silica by hydrogen is accompanied by volatilization. Therefore, weight loss measurements provide a useful metric for quantifying the extent of reduction.

The weight change of silica as a function of the time for the pure sample and the samples mixed with 5 and 10% hematite respectively can be seen in Figure 4. Pure silica experienced only a very minor mass loss: even after 100 h, it was only 0.31%. The approximately linear trend suggests that the reduction kinetics is surface-controlled.

Fig. 4: Mass loss of the pure SiO_2 sample, and the samples mixed with 5 and 10% Fe_2O_3 , as a function of time. The samples were exposed to an atmosphere of 100% H_2 at 1200 °C.

The mass loss of silica in the samples where it was mixed with Fe_2O_3 was calculated using the equation below:

$$\Delta m_{\text{silica}} = \Delta m_{\text{total}} - 30.1\% \times m_{0,\text{hematite}}, \quad (3)$$

where Δm_{silica} is the mass change of silica, Δm_{total} is the total mass change of the sample, and $m_{0,\text{hematite}}$ is the initial mass of hematite in the sample. As the pure hematite samples were observed to be fully reduced in all trials, it was assumed that Fe_2O_3 would also fully reduce when mixed with SiO_2 , with a corresponding mass loss of 30.1%. This consideration is supported by a visual observation of metallic iron in the mixed samples, as well as by SEM analyses (an example of which can be seen in Figure 5). Only metallic iron remained after hydrogen exposure; no hematite was detected.

Figure 4 shows that the mass loss of silica is significantly higher when it is mixed with hematite. For instance, while pure SiO_2 lost 0.31% of its weight after 100 h, SiO_2 mixed with 10% hematite lost 1.27% of its weight. This provides evidence that iron can catalyze the reduction of silica by hydrogen, likely the metallic iron that is formed after hematite is reduced. It is known that transition metals such as Fe can dissociate the hydrogen molecule under certain conditions. In these metals, the s electrons can revert to the unfilled d-states, which counteracts the Pauli repulsion between the s electrons of the metal and those of the hydrogen molecule. The dissociation of hydrogen produces reactive hydrogen radicals (H^*), which will proceed to reduce SiO_2 [6 - 8].

Figure 4 indicates that the silica reduction is more extensive in samples containing 10% Fe_2O_3 compared with

those with 5%. The reduction kinetics seems to have a decelerating trend, and additional data is needed to determine whether the weight loss eventually flattens out.

Fig. 5 – Sample with 95% SiO_2 and 5% Fe_2O_3 exposed to 100% H_2 at 1200 °C for 25 h; 1) is metallic iron and 2) is silica.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

These preliminary results provide evidence that metallic iron can catalyze the corrosion of SiO_2 by hydrogen. The proposed underlying mechanism is the splitting of the H_2 molecule into hydrogen radicals, which react more readily with silica. This implies that iron impurities that naturally occur in refractory raw materials could be detrimental to their corrosion resistance under H_2 atmospheres.

Further trials are now being carried out to provide a better understanding of the kinetics of the reduction of silica by hydrogen in the presence of metallic iron, with different iron amounts, longer H_2 exposure times, and at different temperatures. Moreover, investigations with model castables having different iron impurity contents will help to translate these findings into refractory applications.

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